

Okute Festival Among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria

By Ebenezer Elesemoyo, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religious Traditions, Yoruba Religions, Language, Atlantic-Congo, Volta-Congo, Benue-Congo, Defoid, Yoruboid, Edekiri, Ede, Eastern Ede, Southeastern Ede, Nuclear Yoruba, Lucumi-Yoruba, Yoruba, Ikale, Ikale Religion

Okute Festival is a ritual practice among the Ikale sub-group of the Yoruba ethnicity which began as a result of an event which took place sometimes in 1522; an invasion in Old Arogbo-Ule. One of the generals who migrated from Benin Kingdom established his kingdom around the coast roughly mid point between Benin and Lagos and continued to wax strong in terms of influence and wealth. The King with the title Larogbo was very prominent and received tribute and royalties from merchants plying this coastal region adjoining the Atlantic Ocean. His wealth and military power conferred significant influence on him in the region. As a result, every kingdom around (Benin Kingdom inclusive) dreaded him. Oral tradition has it that their neighbours, the Ilaje people had a saying that ... where there is war, there you will find Larogbo. In fact, he was believed to have had a hand in any internal crises of any neighbouring kingdom. The overbearing influence of Larogbo made the Benin Kingdom to go in alliance with the Portuguese who had significant trading interest in the area and to whom Larogbo's influence had been a concern. To curb Larogbo's influence, his neighbours forged an alliance and waged a war against Larogbo's Kingdom during and Ere Festival. History has it that One of Larogbo's daughters was married to one of the Portuguese, though she tried to warn her dad having been aware of the plot, the alliance forbade her from expressly leaking the impending catastrophe that would be visited on her father and his kingdom. The love of her people compelled her to resolve to singing some warning songs during the festival. Unfortunately, the King was not attentive enough to his daughter's warnings due to the celebration. The attack commenced and decimated the kingdom. Many of the survivors fled southward, some escaped by crossing the Oluwa River and finally settled in a place called Idepe-Okitipupa today. The Okute festival and the rituals associated with it is a remembrance of this sad event, which is then observed every year before Ere festival among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa and those of Akotogbo who are also descendants of Larogbo. Because the King was distracted by the celebration characterised by singing, dancing and all forms of celebration, Okute Festival is then observed in sobriety. The festival and its ritual observances occupy a significant place in the history, formation and spiritual unity of the community. As the most important annual ritual ceremony in the community, every member of the town is required to prepare for the rituals and make themselves available for its smooth running as any failure before, during and immediately after the ritual celebration is considered a collective failure which may bring bad omen to the entire clan. No form of drumming is permitted in any part of the community for the period of the festival which usually lasted for three months. The duration of the festival has only been reduced to two weeks in recent decades in consideration of members of the community who now hold allegiance to other faiths.

Date Range: 1522 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Region tags: Southwest Nigeria, Nigeria, Oyo state, Ogun State, Ekiti State, Osun state, Osun State, Kwara state, Lagos, Ondo state, Oyo state

This map includes the approximate regions of Southwest/Western Nigeria and is comprised of the following states: Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti, and Benin states. The additional inclusion of the West Central region state of Kwara is to the north of these states.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

Notes: Some aspects of the rituals are performed behind closed doors while others are performed within the palace compound

↳ Enclosed?

– Yes

Notes: Some aspects of the rituals associated with the festivals are performed in a private room within the palace

↳ Elevated?

– No

↳ By a body of water?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not connected to water at all.

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed near fire, volcano, lava or any human-made fire

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: The room is considered sacred and as a result secluded from public

↳ Other [Specify]

–Specify: The ritual is observed in an enclosed room inside the palace

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– Yes

Notes: some of the rites are performed within a private room inside the palace

↳ Underground?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building)

– No

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

Notes: The concluding rite is performed in an open space within the palace compound

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Notes: The rituals performed in the public space are made open to the public without any form of restriction. However, the one performed in the room within the palace are limited to the

custodians of the ritual

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: There are rituals that are carried out in private, while the celebration to cap it up is carried out within the compound of the palace where others can see.

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is performed in a private room within the palace

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: The private room is considered sacred

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

Notes: The site is temporal in terms of arrangement, but the arrangement is made to a permanence site for the purpose of the ritual

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

Notes: The room is a permanent space within the palace where other rituals could be performed,

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Notes: While the private room is permanent, the compound is temporarily utilised

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Notes: The site is independent of the ritual although it is used for it.

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: The private room is associated with the ancestors, more importantly the founding fathers who suffered the attack of the allied forces

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– No

Notes: The site is not a representative of any metaphysical or physical place. It is constructed as a designated place for some private rituals

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Notes: The site is not in anyway connected to the sun, stars or other astronomical features

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Notes: The site is not particularly constructed towards any directional orientation

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The site is not oriented to any landforms

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is observed once in a year, more often between March and late April

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is observed between March and late April every year

↳ Daily:

– No

Notes: The ritual are not observed daily, rather it is performed annually

↳ Weekly:

– No

Notes: The ritual are not observed weekly, rather it is performed annually

↳ Seasonally:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not observed seasonally, rather it is performed annually

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Notes: The ritual are not observed once in an individual lifetime, rather it is performed annually because it is communal, not individualistic

↳ Special events/occasions:

– No

Notes: The rituals are not special events/occasion, but performed annually. It is a communal ritual type performed/observed by the entire community

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

Notes: The rituals are not observed as life circle events, but an annual ritual in remembrance of a certain event in the past

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve Ad hoc

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Notes: The ritual is usually observed between March and April within the last decade

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– No

Notes: The ritual performance is not specified in terms of hours, but days.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– No

Notes: The ritual is mostly performed by indigenous people alone

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed on the basis of specialist-patient orientation

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

Notes: There are a lot of participants who are not ritual specialists.

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The numbers of participant involved in the ritual is not determined

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is predominantly performed by men except for the capping rite usually performed within the compound of the palace. However, women still in their procreation years are advised to leave the vicinity towards the end of the public rite, because it is believed that songs and chats to be performed at those times have the force to prevent them from ever getting pregnant if they remain within the spiritually charged environment where the ritual is taking place.

↳ Male:

– Yes

Notes: Men are the dominant participants

↳ Female:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not include female except in the capping celebration

↳ Transgender:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Non-binary:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The ritual participant cut across different ages

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Participant of the ritual have none other role than to observe and dance or clap their hands to the rhythm of the songs

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Participant are insiders in the sense that they are to be indigenous members of the community

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Participant are not required to be outsiders, as both outsiders and insiders are present during the ritual

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Participant are not necessarily required to be specialist before they can participate in the ritual

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: The participants are both specialists and non-specialists

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: Women are restricted from participating in the main rituals and also some aspect of the closing celebration. Especially women still with the intention of procreation

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings believed to be present during the ritual are ancestors, but are not actors in the ritual

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve non-human or organic entities

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve abiotic or inorganic entities

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

Notes: The divine/spiritual beings are mostly ancestors

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

Notes: The high god is not conceived to be a performer at the ritual celebration

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural being believed to be present are mostly ancestors, but are not performers

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings are believed to be transformed beings

↳ Others:

– No

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– No

Notes: There are no spectators other than media personnel invited to cover the ritual

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– Yes

Notes: other than the specialist and coordinators, individuals' participation is at will, not enforced

↳ Is it individually determined:

– No

Notes: Except for the King, Ijama, Chiefs and Priests

↳ Is it communally determined:

– Yes [specify]: Participation in the ritual are only communally determined for the category mentioned above

Is participation obligatory?

– No

Notes: Participation in the ritual is not obligatory

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is part of a series of events

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– Yes

Notes: As a result of an invasion that left many of the clan dead which then became a memory and subsequently commemorated by the survivors and generations after

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed as part of seasonal change

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed in response to natural events, rather in response to human made event.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is in response to the death of a large number of a certain clan

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed in reaction to an ominous event

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed during a specific life stage

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is part of series of rituals

Does it involve ritual correction?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve ritual correction; rather, it is a memorial for a sad event in the past

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Notes: The ritual is mostly sponsored by the community, and occasionally by business and voluntary donors

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– No

Notes: The purpose of the ritual is not for maintenance, rather, a memorial

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– No

Notes: The purpose is not to cause change but a memorial

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: it involves both the physical and the spiritual world of the ancestors

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

Notes: it involves divine and spiritual beings who are mostly ancestors of the people

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with non-human organic entities, but to human, who are the forebears of the people

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

Notes: The ritual is not abiotic/inorganic entities, but to human, who are the forebears of the people

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not ecological but to human, who are the forebears of the people

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not about transformed humans but to human, who are the forebears of the people

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– Yes

Notes: It retells a certain ugly story of the people. A retelling of sadness, death, loss and destruction

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: a remembrance and moment of reflection on the past. The goal includes moments of reflection and prayers for the community

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: It is a moment of sober reflection and prayer

↳ For deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: It is centred around reflections on their ancestors who died in an unanticipated attack by the Benin allied forces

↳ For ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Who died in the invasion of the ancient town by the Benin and Portuguese allied forces

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not for non-human, organic entities but to humans, who are the forebears of the people

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not for abiotic or inorganic entities but to humans who are the forebears of the people

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not for divine/spiritual beings but to human who are the forebears of the people

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not for transformed/self-cultivated humans but to human, who are the forebears of the people

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

Notes: The goal of the ritual is not for cultural product but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portugese attack

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– No

Notes: The goal of the ritual is not for propitiation but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

Notes: domestication of agents is not the goal of the ritual but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to gain information but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for cosmic maintenance but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– No

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed for purification

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for exorcism purposes.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for health/ healing purpose but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

Notes: It provides an opportunity for the community to retell the sad story of its invasion in ancient times and as a means of passing the story of the ugly event down to younger generations

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practice to obtain luck, rather as a memorial

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not a naming ritual, rather a memorial

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to improve the community's mode of subsistence. It is a memorial

event/ritual

→ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to induce harm, rather it is a memorial

→ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for the purpose of protection

→ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not a ritual contest

→ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with craft practices, but the death of a large number of member of the clan

→ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with infanticide but a memorial of their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

→ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

Notes: the ritual is not connected to gambling or a game of chance

→ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with travel but a memorial of their forebears who died in the

Benin-Portuguese attack

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with social relations, but family relations

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for wealth accumulation or for the purpose of achieving success. It is performed as a memorial for their forebears who died in the Benin-Portuguese attack

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not to assess causal efficacy

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Sound is allowed just before the ceremony is called to order and the opening rite is performed. This is usually before the pronouncement of the ban on drumming. Drumming is again allowed in the community after the closing rites are performed. When the ceremony ends, the ban is lifted and activities like drumming are once again allowed to take place.

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Notes: it is music in the local community and rendered in the dialect of the community

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

Notes: series of dancing movements are involved, determined by the rhythm of the music and the dance

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

Notes: The songs are performed orally and accompanied by dances and drumming

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– Yes

Notes: it is usually performed by a group of singers who are mostly high chiefs

↳ Is it individual?

– No

Notes: The performance is not individual, rather it is done collectively by the entire group

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

Notes: It involves call and response for some of the songs

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

Notes: it usually involves a lot of singing

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

Notes: Chanting is involved in the rituals. This happens when the panegyrics of the community is performed. There are moments when the King praise is also chanted.

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

Notes: A lot of prayers are made for the King, the High Chiefs, the Chiefs and the community at large

↳ It involves mantras:

– No

Notes: The singing performance does not involve mantras

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– Yes

Notes: The mood often changes from sad to joy and so on

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– Yes

Notes: It involves story telling in the form of songs, recounting events of the past

↳ It involves whistling:

– No

Notes: The performance does not involve whistling

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– Yes

Notes: yes, mostly in indigenous language

↳ How many individuals are involved in creating the vocalizations?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound scripted?

– No

Notes: Sound is not scripted

↳ Is the sound semantic?

– Yes

Notes: The songs are mostly in Ikale dialect. However, the standard Yoruba language too is spoken at some point during the ritual celebration.

↳ How many languages are used in the ritual?

– Specify: 2

Notes: Ikale and Yoruba

↳ Which language(s) are used in the ritual?

– Specify: Ikale and Yoruba

↳ Is the language(s) confined to the ritual:

– No

Notes: The language are everyday language used by the Ikale and Yoruba people

↳ Is it esoteric ritual language:

– No

Notes: The language is not esoteric ritual language

↳ Is it esoteric divine language (i.e., speaking in tongues):

– No

Notes: The language is not esoteric divine language

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not mimetic in nature

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: It is not restricted to ritual use

↳ Is it specifically carried out by ritual specialists?

– Yes

Notes: The performance are mostly carried out by the ritual specialist such as

Abore Okute, The Ijama (High Chiefs), The Ijoye (Chiefs)

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: It does not require formal training, rather it requires indigenous training

↳ Do the vocalizations change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The specific song being sung at each point during the ritual usually determines the vocalisations at every stage of the rituals

↳ Is the change in vocalization correlated to the stage(s) of the ritual?

– No

Notes: No but to the nature of the song being sang

↳ Is there musical texture in the loud vocalizations?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by pitch?

– No

Notes: The vocalization of the music are not regulated by pitch

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

Notes: The rhythm of the music determines the vocalisations

↳ Do they have a pulse?

– No

Notes: Rhythm do not have a pulse

↳ Do they involve codified patterns?

– No

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Specify: The rythm is determined by the song

↳ Are the vocalizations considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Because the rituals involve a lot of singing, vocalisation is also very integral

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– Yes

Notes: such as clapping

↳ Does the sound involve hand movement?

– Yes

Notes: clapping of the hands

↳ Does it involve clapping?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve body concussion?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve body concussion

↳ Does the sound involve feet movement?

– Yes

Notes: It involves dance steps of different kinds

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing the sound:
– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound/movement scripted?
– No
Notes: The sounds or movements are not scripted but rhythmic

↳ Is the sounds/movement semantic?
– No
Notes: The sound or movement are is not semantic

↳ Is the sounds/movement mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?
– No
Notes: The sound and movement are not mimetic

↳ Is this sound/movement restricted to ritual use?
– Yes
Notes: To a large extend, the sounds/movements are restricted to ritual use. One does not hear such sounds/song outside the time and space of the ritual celebrations.

↳ Is the sound/movement carried out by specialists?
– Yes
Notes: Most of the songs are only known by the specialist

↳ Does it require formal training?
– No
Notes: The performance does not require a formal training, rather it requires indigenous model of training

↳ Does the sound/movement change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Sound and movement depend on the song, rhythm, and drums

↳ Is the change correlated to the stage of the ritual?

– No

Notes: The change of the movement corresponded to the song being sang

↳ Is there musical texture in the sound?

– No

Notes: Musical texture is not required in the sound

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– No

Notes: The music is not regulated by speech

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

Notes: The song is regulated by the rhythm

↳ Is there a pulse?

– No

Notes: There are no pulse in the rhythm of the music

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– No

Notes: Music does not involve codified patterns

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: It is determined by the song being sang

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The songs contain the myth of the rituals and the history of the community

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

↳ Does the sound involve conscious agency?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There are wooden and metal instruments used to strike one another to accompany the music

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

Notes: There are no membranophone

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– No

Notes: They are not idiophone

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

Notes: They are not aerophone

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

Notes: They are not chordophone

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

Notes: They are not electrophone

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– Yes

Notes: They include drums, wood, tambourine, gong

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– No

Notes: There are no specific number required for producing instrumental sounds

↳ Is it scripted?

– No

Notes: Instrumental sound are not scripted

↳ Is it semantic?

– Yes

Notes: involves the dialect of the people

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

Notes: It is not mimetic in any form

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: It is not restricted to ritual use

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: It does not require formal training, rather, it requires indigenous training

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– No

Notes: it is determined by the song

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– No

Notes: It does not require musical texture

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– No

Notes: The sound is not regulated by pitch

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– No

Notes: The music does not involve pulse

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– No

Notes: It does not involve codified/non-codified patterns

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: influenced by the nature of the song

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: dancing of different kinds are involved

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: the movement are considered as dance

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

Notes: the sound determines the movement

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Notes: wood, metal, tambourine, gong among others

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– N/A

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed regalia or ornament used for the ritual

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Wooden sculpture called bobo to represent dead body

↳ Are they totems:

– Yes

Notes: There is an object carved in human shape to depict the dead members of the clan. Also drum is used both at the beginning and at the end of the rituals. Both objects constitute important component in the ritual

↳ Are they religious icons:

– Yes

Notes: both object are considered sacred and religious icons

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

Notes: They are not fetishes

↳ Are they vessels:

– No

Notes: They are not vessels

↳ Are they masks:

– No

Notes: participant are not masked

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– No

Notes: There are no banner or flag involved

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– Yes

Notes: Bobo is laid on the floor like a corpse rapped in white clothing

↳ Are they sound-producing:

– Yes

Notes: While the drum is sound-producing, the other object called Bobo is not.

↳ Are they divination tools:

– No

Notes: There are no divination tools involved

↳ Are they drug paraphenalia:

– No

Notes: There are no drug parapenalia

↳ Are they cutting devices:

– No

Notes: There are no cutting devices involved in the ritual

↳ Are they sceptres/wands:

– No

Notes: There are no scepters or wands required in the ritual performance

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– No

Notes: Text are not used during the rituals

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– No

Notes: Paintings are not used during the ritual

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Technological tools are not used in the ritual

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Plants are used in the ritual

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Animals are not required during the rituals

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Human parts are not required during the ritual

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: Bodily fluid are not also used during the ritual

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no topical applications involved during the rituals

↳ Is water used?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed use of water during the ritual

↳ Is earth used?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed use of earth during the ritual

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed use of mirror during the rituals

↳ Are textiles used?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed use of textile during the performance of the ritual

↳ Is fire used?

– No

Notes: There is no prescribed use of fire during the performance of the ritual

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual celebration features the consumption of Kolanut, palm wine and alcohol.

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

↳ Is food consumed?

– No

Notes: There is no feasting during the rituals.

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– No

Notes: There is no feasting during the rituals.

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no use of psychoactive substance in the ritual

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: kola nuts and palm wine

↳ Is it smoked:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not smoked but eaten

↳ Is it ingested:

– No

Notes: The kolanut is not ingested but eaten

↳ Is it applied topically:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not topically applied but eaten

↳ Is it chewed:

– Yes

Notes: Substances like kolanut are frequently chewed and alcohol often drunk to make prayers for the community

↳ Is it a suppository:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is chewed and eaten during the ritual celebration.

↳ Is it snorted:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not snorted but chewed and eaten

↳ Is it injected:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not injected but chewed and eaten

↳ Is it offered into the fire:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not offered into fire but chewed and eaten

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:

– No

Notes: Kolanut is not offered to non-human, animal or natural features but chewed and eaten

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– No

Notes: There is no form of prescribed fast towards the ritual

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

Notes: it does not cause vomiting

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no other food substances used in the ritual

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Notes: The substance is not shared from communal vessel or implement

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not ignite any form of altered state of consciousness

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no form of offerings prescribed to be involved as part of the ritual

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no non-normative practices involved in the ritual

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: it is a stand-alone ritual, although it has a series of rites

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Although the ritual stands on its own, it nonetheless dovetails into others which combine to make the community enjoy its uniqueness. So, it stands alone but forms part of a larger series of rituals that combine to give the community its unique experience.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not include some repetition

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– Yes

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– High

Notes: The features of the ritual have practically remained the same over time.

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– Medium

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– Medium

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity

– High

Notes: Members of the community are forbidden from beating the drum throughout the period of the festival

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no synchrony in the performance of the ritual

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no entrainment in the performance of the ritual

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Coordination is done by the King, Ijama (High Chiefs), Chief and Okute Priest

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Younger specialists are taught the songs in the weeks preceding the event

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– N/A

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

Notes: There are preparations like learning of songs

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– No

Notes: There are no requirements of fasting prescribed for the performance of the ritual

↳ Does it involve purification:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve purification

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual involves learning of songs by younger specialist

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve penance of any kind

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Notes: The ritual performance does not involve abstention of any kind

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is often handled by the priest of Okute and the Ijama who are readily expert in the process of the rituals

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Cost is minimal since no proper meal is required

↳ In local currency:

– N/A

Notes: The cost is minimal as the festival does not involve food consumption, rather a moment of reflection

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– N/A

↳ Other measure of cost:

– N/A

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Vertical

– Horizontal

– Esoteric

– Exoteric

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

– Through social imitation

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

- Myth or legend
- Religious specialists
- Political leader(s)
- Social

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Okute Festival Among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria, Ogen, Olukoya. "Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction Among the Idepe-ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland" 39 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1353/hia.2012.0002>.

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